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The Development of Engineering Creativity Scale

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to develop an instrument to measure the quality and pattern of engineering creativity in university students in Taiwan and to investigate its reliability and validity. A scale named the “Engineering Creativity scale” was developed with two sub-tests: Design in Generating Sound and Design a Car. The items and framework of the scale were derived and revised from Charyton’s [1] and Yeh’s [8] studies with minor changes according to the Mandarin usage and local culture.

One hundred eighty-eight undergraduate students from a university in Taiwan were recruited as participants in April, 2017. The results indicated that the test-retest stability, internal consistency and content validity are satisfactory. The implications of this study for further research to establish the Engineering Creativity Scale and engineering creativity teaching and learning are discussed.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Educational Research, Attractiveness of Engineering Education, Skills and Engineering Education

Keywords: Engineering creativity, Scale, University students

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, creativity has become one of the most important issues in engineering education in Taiwan. Many trans-disciplinary programs in Taiwan have focused on the subject and hundreds of web pages display information on how to be more creative and achieve innovation in engineering. To understand and evaluate the quality and pattern of engineering creativity in university students in Taiwan, a trustworthy, reliable and valid creativity instrument is needed to meet the needs of practice and research purposes. The purpose of this study was to develop the Engineering Creativity Scale for measuring university students’ engineering creativity and to analyze the psychometric properties of the scale.

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TEST

One of the most common frameworks for creative thinking processes, described by Torrance [6], consists of four aspects: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. Fluency refers to the production of a great number of ideas or alternate solutions to a problem. Flexibility refers to the production of ideas that show a variety of possibilities or realms of thought. Originality involves the production of ideas that are unique or unusual. Elaboration is the process of enhancing ideas by providing

more detail.

Recently, engineers not only need to address esthetics like artists, but they also need to solve problems, prevent potential problems, and address utility within the constraints and parameters that have been designated [1]. These aspects of creativity have been described as “functional creativity” [4]. Functional creativity means that products designed by engineers typically serve a functional and useful purpose. Building on this, problem-finding offers another avenue for increasing creative production [5]. Problem-finding and problem-solving are skills often found in and commonly associated with art, yet are also necessary in science and engineering. However, these attributes have not been specifically measured traditionally and, more recently, in engineering creativity. Such attributes need to be assessed and further developed by appropriate educational intervention activities [4]. Torrance’s four dimensions (fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration) and their usefulness were adapted in this study as central to the development of the theoretical framework of a scale, namely, the Engineering Creativity Scale.

The “Engineering Creativity Scale” consists of two sub-tests: “Design of generating sound” and “Design a car” which were derived and revised from Charyton’s [1] and Yeh’s [8] studies with minor changes according to the Mandarin usage and local culture. The “Design in Generating Sound” was designated to ask subjects to draw two designs based on two 3D images. The subjects were also asked to describe their designs by answering the following questions: “what is your design?”, “what are the materials of your designs?”, “what are the problems solved with your designs?”, and “who will be users of your designs?”. The second sub-test, “Design a Car”, was designated to ask subjects to draw a car using their imagination and design. Then the subjects were asked to describe the features and specifics of the car they designed. The Engineering Creativity Scale” is shown in Appendix 1.

The test was designed for group administration. The test time limit is 30 minutes (10 minutes for Design in Generating Sound; 20 minutes for Design a Car). The draft version of the test was given to 6 university students (3 males and 3 females) to measure the face validity of the scale. In order to estimate the psychometrics of the scale, a sample of 188 university students in a local university were recruited as participants. Among these participants, 22 of them were administered a two-week test/re-test process for examining the stability of the scale, and 28 participants’ Engineering Creativity Scales were scored by 4 trained scorer (one educational doctoral candidate and three electrical engineering graduate students) for examining the inter-rater reliability of the scale.

SCORING PROCEDURE

In this study, the answers of participants’ Engineering Creativity Scales were

scored by one educational doctoral candidate and three electrical engineering master graduate students, and they had been trained by this paper's authors to learn how to score the engineering creativity scale within the previous two months. The following procedure steps were used to score each subject's answer. The Design in Generating Sound consisted of four dimensions: fluency, flexibility, originality, and usefulness. Fluency was computed by the number of ideas on the sketch, description, materials, problems solved, and users. Flexibility was counted by the number of different categories, types, or classifications of responses. Originality was scored by an 11-point scale. The Usefulness is scored by a 5-point scale. At first, D1 and D2 were scored separately, and then sum of D1 and D2 was computed for each dimension, separately.

The Design a Car" included four dimensions: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. The fluency score was given simply by counting all of the valid responses given by the subjects. The flexibility score was given by counting the numbers of category of students' answers on the car features. The originality score was developed from a tabulation of the frequency of all of the responses obtained. Frequencies and percentages of each response were computed. Among all answers, 2 points were given to a special answer for the originality score when the probability of this answer was smaller than 5%. One point was given to an answer of which the probability is between 5% and 10%. The elaboration is obtained by counting the numbers of car specifies given by subjects.

Finally, the total score of "Design of Generating Sound" for each subject was computed by summing of his/ her T scores of fluency, flexibility, originality, and usefulness. The total score of "Design a Car" was computed by summing the T scores of fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. The total scores of engineering creativity for each subject are computed by averaging scores of these two subtests' scores.

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY ANALYSES.

1 Reliability

1.1 Internal consistency reliability

The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients among dimensions (fluency, flexibility, originality, elaboration, and usefulness) and total score were calculated. The results are shown in Table 1. The correlation coefficients between dimensions and total score vary from 0.23 to 0.94, which are relatively high. Most of the correlations coefficients are significant at the 0.001 level except the correlation between usefulness and elaboration

Table 1. The internal consistency reliability of ECS (n=188)

Variable	Fluency	Flexibility	Originality	Elaboration	Usefulness	Total Score
Fluency	1					
Flexibility	.88***	1				
Originality	.79***	.72***	1			
Elaboration	.68***	.58***	.64***	1		
Usefulness	.50***	.46***	.61***	.23***	1	
Total Score	.94***	.90***	.91***	.74***	.65***	1

*** $p < .01$

1.2 Test/re-test reliability

The results of the test/re-test reliability are shown in Table 2. The correlations coefficients between the first test and retest are significant among fluency, flexibility, originality, and total scores ($r(22) = .44 - .56, p < .05$). The results of this study indicated that the engineer creativity scales developed in this study has a good stability.

Table 2. The test-retest reliability of the ECS (n = 22)

Variable	Re-test					
	Fluency	Flexibility	Originality	Elaboration	Usefulness	Total Score
Fluency	.50*					
Flexibility		.44*				
Originality			.56**			
Elaboration				.38		
Usefulness					.21	
Total Score						.51*

* $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$

1.3 Inter-rater reliability

The results of the inter-rater reliability are shown in Table 3. The Kendall's W coefficients of fluency, flexibility, originality, elaboration and total scores are between .47 and .97, which are significant at the .01 and .001 level. The results of this study indicated that the scoring criteria of the engineering creativity scale between different scorers are consistent.

Table 3. The inter-rater reliability of the ECS

	Fluency	Flexibility	Originality	Elaboration	Usefulness	Total Score
Kendall's W	.97***	.91***	.75***	.93***	.47**	.92***
Chi-Square	105.04***	97.85***	81.17***	100.45***	50.78**	99.46***
df	27	27	27	27	27	27

Note: Scorer=4; n=28 ** $p < .01$ *** $p < .001$

2 Content validity

Content validity refers to the extent to which a measure represents all facets of a given construct. Content validity requires the use of recognized subject matter experts to evaluate whether test items assess defined content and more rigorous statistical tests than does the assessment of face validity. An initial pool of 4 subtests were written to reflect the logical and semantic content of the concept of creativity based on relevant past sources and engineering creativity research and on dictionary definition. Nine experts or university professors in engineering, education, or psychology were asked to determine content validity of the four initial subtests. The content of the Engineering Creativity Scale has been modified based on the experts' suggestions and comments. From the initial 4 subtests, two of them were chosen for use in this study.

SUMMARY AND FURTHER WORK

The purpose of this study was to develop the Engineering Creativity Scale for university students in Taiwan and to investigate its reliability and validity. Based on the creativity structure model and related theory, the Engineering Creativity Scale was developed to consist of two subtests: "Design in Generating Sound" and "Design a Car". These two subtests were designed to measure five aspects: fluency, flexibility, originality, elaboration, and usefulness. The internal consistency, test-retest reliability, interrater reliability and content validity are found to be satisfactory.

This study proposes some suggestions for engineering learning and teaching, and further research. First, a parallel form of the current scale should be developed in order to estimate the alternate-forms of reliability. Second, the criterion-related validity with existing tests, such as the Torrance Test of Creative Thinking [6] needs to be estimated in order to confirm the criterion-related validity of the engineering creativity scale for assessing creativity of university students in Taiwan. Third, further research should explore the relationships between different university students' backgrounds and engineering creativity using the Engineer Creativity Scale that was developed in this study. Matters that could be explored might include: the relationships between grade, school type, the field of study, family background and engineering creativity.

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Appendix 1

I. Design of Generating Sound (10 minutes max)

Below you find 2 shapes. At seeing these two shapes, you might have some ideas popping up. Be creative, use your imagination and see if you can come up with “a design that generates sound.” These 2 shapes can be of any material and size of your choice, and can be either solid or hollow. However, each shape can be used only once. Please make sure that you include the drawing of the design, description of the design, the materials used (the texture), problems with which the design may be solved and people who may find the design handy.

Your design	1	2

Description of your design		
Materials used / texture		
Problem with which design can be solved		
Potential users / why they may find the design handy		

II · Design a Car (1) Drawing a car (10 minutes max)

What would you do if invited to design a car? You are encouraged to incorporate as many different ideas as possible. Draw your design below and name the overall outlook and every feature included. Lastly, give the whole design/model a creative name as well.

Name of the model of the car :

II · Design a Car (2) Special features of the car (10 minutes max)

Please write down special features the car may have on the left, and on the right, specify with what objects or facilities you may make the special features possible. If you missed anything in the previous section, you may include them here. You may check back on your design but do not add anything else on the done design. The more you list here, the better.

Features (ex: ... may allow; ... can)	Specify (what may be needed , ex : it needs..)
ex : fire missiles	Need missiles · launcher
1.	
2	
3	

4	
5	